

Ciung Wanara (2022 - 2023)

"Ciung Wanara" is an interactive audiovisual composition inspired by Indonesian shadow puppet battles. The performance takes a semantic approach, featuring two distinct rooster avatars that respond in real-time to the performer's gestures. The performer uses two avatars controlled by their hand movements to recreate the tale of Ciung Wanara, a wise king and skilled cockfighter who triumphs over an evil sorcerer. The Sabetan technique of Indonesia Wayang Kulit and the FluComa machine learning library allows the performer to simultaneously generate and control digital sound synthesis, multi-channel spatialization, and visuals.

The presentation of two avatars with a clear narrative, generated by the performer's hand gestures, creates a unique audio-visual experience not commonly seen in conventional forms of audiovisual composition. This leads to a uniquely immersive and interactive experience not only between the performer and composition but also with the audience.

Link to Audiovisual Material (Ciung Wanara):

<https://youtu.be/UFeEJXj0gw?si=5d3ckqvfPTaJeKMK>

“Ciung Wanara” Technical Rider for Live Performance

I. Video Equipment:

- High-quality video projector (minimum resolution: 1920x1080, minimum brightness: 5000 lumens) OR LED screen (minimum size: 12ft x 7ft)
- HDMI cable/connection for video input

II. Stage Setup & Furniture:

- Sturdy table desk (minimum dimensions: 6ft x 2.5ft) for laptop, soundcard, and other equipment
- Comfortable, adjustable-height chair for the performer

III. Power Requirements:

- One (1) dedicated power circuit (15-20 amp) for laptop, soundcard, and two (2) additional devices
- At least four (4) power outlets on or near the table desk
- Extension cords and power strips as needed

IV. Audio Equipment:

- Quadraphonic speaker system (four (4) full-range speakers) with a frequency response of 60Hz-20kHz, capable of handling 1000W RMS each
- One (1) high-quality subwoofer capable of handling 1000W RMS, with a frequency response of 30Hz-200Hz
- Required cables and connectors for quadraphonic setup and subwoofer integration

V. Stage Planning

